

Challenges of Implementing Zero Waste Strategies in the Gastronomy Industry

Claus-Heinrich Daub¹[0000-0002-6235-9970], Carole Gerhard¹[0000-0001-6769-1860] and Monisser Altermatt¹

¹ Institute of Management, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, Bahnhofstrasse 6, 5210 Windisch, Switzerland

Abstract. This case tells the story of the Café spurlos which aims at becoming a zero waste business and thus making a significant contribution to combating one of the greatest challenges facing society today: the transformation of the economic system into a circular economy. Besides the COVID-crisis and the thereof resulting issues, the café also faces challenges related to its vision of incorporating the zero waste philosophy in its concept. The case explores the complexity of zero waste, analyses further hurdles for zero waste endeavors in the gastronomy industry and illustrates the constant balancing act of social businesses between staying true to one's mission and catering to the needs, wants and expectations of the market.

Keywords: Zero waste, sustainability, gastronomy industry, social entrepreneurship

1 Introduction

It was a beautiful day in February 2020. One of those days that make you aware that spring is just around the corner. Tamara opened the Café spurlos – freely translated to “Café without leaving a trace” – for the first time. It was the start of her mission to run a zero waste restaurant. A place for people to meet, mingle and relax, but also a place where sustainability is in the center of everything. The smell of fresh coffee was in the air and the sound of people chatting and discussing filled the room. That was one year ago. Today, the café is empty. The chairs are on the tables, the coffee machine is still. Far and wide there is not a soul to be seen.

It was most definitely not an easy start for Café spurlos. The COVID-pandemic has hit the gastronomy industry hard. Only a few weeks after its opening, the Swiss government ordered all restaurants to close temporarily. The re-opening was possible later in May, but under strict restrictions. In November 2020, the café had to close down again in face of the second wave of the pandemic. However, the COVID-situation was not the only hurdle for the Café spurlos. It quickly became clear that its vision of becoming a zero waste operation also comes with challenges.

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2 Case Study

2.1 The Story of Café Spurlos

That the Café spurlos shall be as sustainable as possible was kind of an obvious decision. The café was founded by and is located within the Impact Hub Basel, a global network of more than 16'000 members in 100 hubs in over 50 countries worldwide. The Impact Hub Basel has the aspiration of supporting a community of social entrepreneurs and sustainable innovators through events, coworking and a variety of incubator and accelerator programs. All of its activities are centered around the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It was therefore clear that also its café shall be grounded on those values. However, creating as little waste as possible is an ambitious endeavor that requires a lot of know-how. Thus, the Impact Hub Basel decided to get an academic partner on board to observe and test how their vision could come to life in the most effective and efficient way. That is how the “Zero Waste Innovation Lab (ZEWIL)” was born.

The ZEWIL is a state-funded collaboration between the Impact Hub Basel and the University of Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW). The project aims at supporting economical processes and zero waste innovations in the gastronomy industry, which reduce waste and the overall use of resources. The Café spurlos is at the center of the ZEWIL and all activities of the project are structured into four components. Firstly, “research and documentation”, whereby Café spurlos’ concept and business serve as a platform and research object at the same time to test, evaluate and analyze zero waste strategies and solutions in the gastronomy sector with the goal of making the Café spurlos a profitable business – from an economic as well as from an ecological and social point of view. This part of the project is under the responsibility of the FHNW. Secondly, the Impact Hub Basel is in charge of the components “education and awareness” and “innovation and experience”. Thereby, the Impact Hub Basel organizes events and workshops around the findings of the ZEWIL project as well as an accelerator program for entrepreneurs focusing on zero waste in the gastronomy sector. Lastly, the aim is to develop a scalable business model whereby the acquired knowledge can be implemented in the industry through consulting services or similar.

Tamara was very excited to be a part of the ZEWIL as the manager of the Café spurlos. She had previously worked in the gastronomy industry, but it was always her desire to make more of a difference with her work. The ZEWIL seemed like just the right opportunity to do so. She was highly motivated to start this journey towards a zero waste operation and was very happy when Simon joined to support her in the management of the café.

Fig. 1. Tamara and Simon

2.2 Zero Waste – What Does That Actually Mean?

Besides the resulting issues of the COVID-situation, Tamara and Simon also soon faced the first challenges related to their task of incorporating the zero waste philosophy in their concept. Zero waste is not a protected term and as a result, there is no universal definition of it. Therefore, the first question that arose for Tamara and Simon was: “What does it mean to be a zero waste restaurant?” The most widely used and accepted definition of zero waste was developed by the Zero Waste International Alliance (ZWIA) in 2002 and has since been further elaborated. The most current version is as follows:

“Zero Waste: The conservation of all resources by means of responsible production, consumption, reuse, and recovery of products, packaging, and materials without burning and with no discharges to land, water, or air that threaten the environment or human health.” [19]

Therefore, zero waste maximizes recycling, minimizes waste towards zero, decreases consumption and strives towards products that are designed to be reused, regenerated, repaired and recycled internally or back into nature or the marketplace [9]. However, zero waste focuses on all kinds of resources and is therefore closely related to the concept of sustainability, which aims at respecting environmental, social and

economic aspects simultaneously. Also, zero waste refers to the entire value chain of a product – from sourcing all the way to the disposal – and hence also is in line with circular economy principles. Furthermore, the definition of zero waste has evolved over the years and the focus has shifted from recycling to maximizing the reuse of materials and the efficiency thereof.

Moreover, the Zero Waste International Alliance also developed the "Zero Waste Hierarchy", which describes a progression of policies and strategies to support the zero waste system, from highest and best to lowest use of materials [18].

Fig. 2. The Zero Waste Hierarchy 7.0 [18]

While the “Zero Waste Hierarchy” was developed for general application, there are no further guidelines around the concept specifically tailored to the gastronomy industry. More so, zero waste is often equalized with food waste. However, zero waste goes much further than that and includes the conservation of all types of resources involved and used in a restaurant operation – not solely food.

2.3 When Complexity Makes Things Complicated

The managers of Café spurlos began to realize that their ambition of opening a zero waste café was a lot more complicated than they had initially thought. The complexity of the zero waste concept and the fact that the entire value chain of a product has to be considered in order to evaluate its level of sustainability makes it very hard to incorporate and respect zero waste principles in all decisions and activities, Tamara elaborates. Often it is very non-transparent how, where and under which circumstances a product was produced, transported and processed. Really digging into this information is not only complicated, but also extremely time-consuming and not rarely simply impossible. Hence, just sourcing “standard” products from large suppliers is simply the easiest and fastest way. That is one of the reasons why Tamara and Simon think that joining forces is crucial for the gastronomy industry in its striving towards a more sustainable future. At the moment, there is no real sharing of knowledge between hospitality organizations around the topic. That is particularly relevant given that the hospitality industry in Switzerland is a distinct SME sector, dominated by independent micro-enterprises with only very few employees [15, 7]. As a result, those types of operations also only have very little negotiation power in terms of sustainability and zero waste policies, regulations and standards with their respective suppliers. Moreover, it cannot be overlooked that the effort for sourcing a product does not depend on the purchase quantity. Making sure the 2 kilograms of apples you sell in your café per week are as sustainable as possible does take as much time and effort as when you sell 100 kilograms per week. That makes it even more challenging for small operations like the Café spurlos to be truly “zero waste”.

On top of that, legal requirements, particularly related to food safety, often stand in the way of making a restaurant operation more resource-efficient. Simon explains: “Even if you are very determined to reduce food waste, it is not easy. The options are limited because under the Swiss food legislations, food that has been presented on a buffet has to be tossed after a certain amount of time and leftovers from i.e. a catering cannot be re-sold.” While those restrictions may make sense from a food safety point of view, they definitely hinder the gastronomy industry in its sustainability endeavors.

2.4 Determining What Is Right

How challenging the complexity of zero waste is became especially visible in the development of the café’s offer. In the conceptualization process, Tamara and Simon asked themselves what products they actually want to put up for sale and according to which standards and criteria they should be chosen. When looking at the “Zero Waste Hierarchy” pyramid, they realized that they were currently on the first stage of the process: “rethink and redesign”. They were trying to put together an offer that conserves and protects all resources in the sense of the zero waste concept. “What even is a zero waste offer? What is a sustainable diet and what would a sustainable food system look like?”, were questions the managers of the café asked themselves. That is when it became apparent how difficult it is to assess the “sustainability” of a product in its entirety, since that is the result of the simultaneous consideration of ecological, social and

economic factors. According to the FAO, economic impacts on sustainable food systems are i.e. profits, generated jobs, tax revenues or food supplies. Environmental impacts can i.e. be the carbon and water footprint, soil health, animal health, food waste, biodiversity or toxicity; whereas social impacts to be mentioned are i.e. added value distribution (gender, youth, indigenous people), cultural traditions, nutrition and health, worker rights or animal welfare [6]. Thus, all of those factors have to be respected and catered to at the same time in order to be as sustainable as possible. Moreover, at the 2010 conference "Biodiversity and Sustainable Diets: United Against Hunger," jointly organized by FAO and Bioversity International, the following definition of sustainable diets was agreed upon:

“Those diets with low environmental impacts which contribute to food and nutrition security and to healthy life for present and future generations. Sustainable diets are protective and respectful of biodiversity and ecosystems, culturally acceptable, accessible, economically fair and affordable; nutritionally adequate, safe and healthy; while optimizing natural and human resources.” [5]

It thus became clear that due to the various factors that need to be taken into account, it is very difficult to establish blanket "rules" that make a culinary offering sustainable. However, three main guiding principles have been identified to be efficient in terms of optimizing the use of resources from a scientific point of view:

1. **Plant-based:** In order to reduce CO₂ emissions as much as possible, a largely "plant-based" food offer is key. Undoubtedly, meat and dairy products cause by far the highest CO₂ emissions of all types of food [14]. Particularly beef has an unsurpassable impact on the planet's greenhouse gas emissions and also requires more water and land in its production than any other single food product [1]. However, when it comes to nutrition, health aspects naturally also play a central role. The EAT-Lancet Commission looked into this very issue and researched what a "Planetary Diet" - a diet that simultaneously offers the most benefits for the environment and for people - should look like. Such a diet should optimize health and thereby enable people to be in a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being while the respective food production should stay within the boundaries defined in order to decrease the risk of irreversible and potentially catastrophic shifts in the Earth system. The Commission concluded that such a diet should be largely plant-based flexitarian and include only a small amount (approximately 13% of the daily caloric intake) of animal products [3].
2. **Seasonality and Regionality:** There are two types of seasonality: globally seasonal (i.e. produced in the natural production season but consumed anywhere in the world) and locally seasonal (produced in the natural production season and consumed in the same region) [11], which is why seasonality and regionality go hand in hand. One would assume that locally seasonal produce is more beneficial from a sustainability point of view. Generally, that is true given that globally local products can have a high environmental cost in the country of production in terms of water or land usage. But the reality is not that simple. Those foods also come with nutritional benefits since they offer a more varied and consistent supply of fresh products all year around

[11]. Moreover, it is widely believed that transportation is a main contributor to the ecological footprint of produce. Research shows that air transport in particular indeed has a strong impact on the ecological balance. However, the vast majority of goods from overseas are transported by ship, which does not have a particularly relevant impact on the footprint [13]. Another factor that can impact the eco-friendliness of seasonal food is whether or not the products were grown in a heated greenhouse [2]. Moreover, the consumption of globally seasonal produce might also support communities in producing countries that highly depend on agricultural trade. However, such food might often be produced under more than problematic working conditions.

That illustrates how many small factors determine the sustainability of a product and thus also makes clear that what is the most resource-friendly option has to be evaluated on an individual case-to-case basis. Overall, it can be said that the consumption of seasonal and local produce only matters little for total CO₂-emissions. The choice of the actual food holds definitely more importance in that regard and a more plant-based diet will therefore always have a much larger impact regardless of seasonality and regionality of the products [14]. However, if one really wants to make difference, one also needs to take care about what animal products are replaced with and under which environmental and social circumstances those have been produced [1].

3. **Fair Production:** Under which conditions food has been produced and whether or not those circumstances can be considered humane, inclusive or fair is extremely hard to evaluate as a consumer and as a restaurant manager alike. However, operating under zero waste principles also includes using human resources as efficiently and sustainably as possible. Therefore, protecting workers' rights and paying adequate salaries to producers are crucial factors [4]. The easiest way to ensure those requirements are met, are respective certifications such as i.e. Fair Trade. However, the vast number of labels and standards arguably guaranteeing fair production can be overwhelming and their effectiveness hard to assess. On top of that, they also come with drawbacks. Producers must meet increasing requirements for certification which comes at a price that is often not feasible for small businesses and farms in developing countries [17]. On the other hand, that of course also results in higher purchasing and respective selling prices of the food products.

2.5 Zero Waste Can Never Be Perfect

When taking a closer look at those three guiding principles, Tamara and Simon learned quickly that in the context of sustainability and zero waste, there is a counter-argument for everything. The vegan diet is the most ecological, but not necessarily the healthiest one. Organic meat is better for animal welfare, but causes more Co₂-emissions per kilogram compared to meat from conventional production. Consuming products from overseas is not necessarily environmental-friendly, but supports communities that highly depend on the export of their agricultural produce. It became obvious that zero

waste can never be objectively perfect. Given the interdisciplinary nature of the sustainability concept, which aims at respecting ecological, social and economic factors equally and at the same time, there will always be certain compromises that have to be made. Moreover, the café also faced the challenge of being economically profitable while incorporating the philosophy of zero waste. “The quality has to be right. If the coffee is super sustainable, sourced fairly and served in a reusable cup but then tastes like crap, nobody is going to come”, says Simon. Moreover, guests also have certain expectations. Even though coffee has to be imported and production conditions might often be critical, it is a product that undoubtedly has to be part of the offer in order for a café to have a chance to be financially successful. The same goes for having a largely plant-based offer. The managers had sincere doubts that their customers would be satisfied with a menu largely free of any animal products. Those dilemmas between customer expectations and sustainable management practices have also been studied in scientific literature. A recent study i.e. has found that particularly young employees in the hospitality industry are eager to incorporate eco-friendliness and thus highly motivated to reduce food waste. However, in pursuit of customer satisfaction through fresh produce, they tend to accept and follow the given cultural workplace waste norms – which do not necessarily aim at reducing food waste - despite their actual beliefs [10].

Tamara and Simon also came to realize that depending on the quantity, sourcing locally can be challenging. Regional produce is limited and therefore, larger amounts are often not available. That makes the sourcing process unpredictable, unreliable and thus even more complex, which can easily scare off restaurants trying to be more sustainable. Sourcing foodstuffs from fair production was important to the café managers too. However, they were also aware that guests are only willing to pay a premium for a sustainable product up to a certain degree.

Undoubtedly, to guarantee that a product is truly and fully sustainable, supply chain transparency is key [8]. The process that a product has undergone before it ended up on a customer’s plate needs to be traceable to ensure that it corresponds with the desired ecological and social standards - and hence zero waste principles - along the entire value chain. Given the immense amount of information and the high level of complexity, that is anything but an easy task. However, recent research suggests that Blockchain technology might be a well-suited tool to enable traceability – and hence transparency – of supply chains [i.e.16]. Moreover, it has been found that Blockchain hence has the potential to increase supply chain sustainability performance [12]. It therefore seems like technology and respective systems hold great potential to profoundly influence the way in which decisions over resource use and commodity trade are made [8] and could therefore also dismantle at least some of the barriers in terms of implementing zero waste strategies in the gastronomy sector. i

Fig. 3. The terrace at Café spurlos

2.6 Excited for the Future

The complexity and the simultaneous interaction of so many individual factors became more and more overwhelming and challenging the further the conceptualization process of the Café spurlos progressed. Evidently, being a zero waste operation is a constant balancing act between staying true to its mission and cater to the wants, needs and expectations of its customers. Also, it became clear to Tamara and Simon that zero waste has boundaries and they have learned quickly that frustration is now part of their job description. However, Tamara says, “zero waste is a matter of the heart. Our motivation is intrinsic, we do this because we believe in the cause, because we want to make an impact.”

Now, in spring 2021, it seems like there is finally light at the end of the COVID-tunnel. The Café spurlos team has made the best use of their forced break and worked out a solid concept for their business. “Once everything is back to normal, we will hit the ground running. This is what we are passionate about - it’s as simple as that”, Tamara concludes. If only it was.

3 Teaching Notes

3.1 Learning Outcomes

The objective of this case study is to expose students to the concept of zero waste and the implementation thereof in the gastronomy industry. Moreover, they will examine the complexity of the zero waste concept and learn more about the challenges and hurdles on the way to incorporating the zero waste philosophy.

3.2 Questions

1. What are the main challenges of conceptualizing a zero waste café?
2. What next steps could Café spurlos take towards their vision of becoming a zero waste operation?
3. To what extent do you think zero waste is achievable and what role does that play in the context of sustainability overall?
4. How do you think the COVID-crisis affects the zero waste movement in the gastronomy sector and beyond?
5. How could technology and particularly the integration thereof help overcoming the identified challenges and make the implementation of zero waste principles more effective and efficient?

3.3 Model Answers and Analysis

1. What are the main challenges of conceptualizing a zero waste café?

The challenges are manifold. Firstly, the fact that “zero waste” is not a protected term and its definition therefore somewhat subjective makes it challenging to even establish the determining factors of what a zero waste café should be and what requirements it should fulfil. Even if one was to come up with a definition, the communication thereof to the customer remains challenging. Another significant hurdle is the complexity of zero waste. The fact that the entire value chain of a product has to be considered in order to evaluate its level of sustainability makes it very hard to incorporate and respect zero waste principles in all decisions and activities. Moreover, information regarding the sustainability of products is untransparent and thus difficult and time-consuming to gather. On the other hand, zero waste centers around reducing all kinds of resources. Hence, social, economic as ecological factors have to be respected simultaneously. As a result, there is a counter-argument for nearly anything in the context of zero waste. On top of that, due to the small-structuredness of the industry, implementing zero waste practices is time-consuming and can potentially be frustrating due to little negotiation power and impact on policies and regulations. Also, there are certain legal requirements that might stand in the way of becoming a more sustainable operation.

2. What next steps could Café spurlos take towards their vision of becoming a zero waste operation?

This question could be answered in many different ways and might stimulate creative solutions and approaches. Potential directions could include the development of a clear concept and a definition of what a zero waste café is in that context, goal setting, measuring waste, community building with other players in the industry, entering partnerships or the development of a circular system. This question might also be a good opportunity to start a discussion around what requirements a zero waste café should fulfil and what social, ecological and economic factors should be considered simultaneously.

3. To what extent do you think zero waste is achievable and what role does that play in the context of sustainability overall?

The case of the Café spurlos has clearly shown that zero waste can never be perfect because of the complexity of the concept and the many different aspects that have to be combined and respected simultaneously. Also, the term zero waste can be confusing because not creating any waste at all seems somewhat utopian and unrealistic. However, the hierarchy of zero waste might be a good indicator of prioritizing different zero waste strategies and might be the best way to optimize one's waste generation and management.

Zero waste is very closely related to the concept of sustainability. In order to achieve sustainability, zero waste practices are inevitable. Therefore, the challenges of implementing both concepts are also very similar. Just like zero waste, sustainability is highly complex and requires to combine a variety of aspects.

4. How do you think the COVID-crisis affects the zero waste movement in the gastronomy sector and beyond?

On the one hand, the COVID-outbreak and the resulting crisis might have increased the awareness for sustainability-related issues and at the same time strengthened people's appreciation, consciousness and mindfulness for both nature and social community. Those changes might also be translated into the gastronomy sector and increase the activities and endeavors related to sustainability and zero waste. On the other hand, the new requirements, circumstances and habits due to the COVID-situation definitely also had negative impacts in terms of waste creation. In the gastronomy industry, especially one-use hygienic items such as masks, paper towels or gloves generate a considerable amount of waste. Not to be forgotten is the take away packaging that has become crucial during COVID and obviously is a very wasteful practice as such.

5. How could technology and particularly the integration thereof help overcoming the identified challenges and make the implementation of zero waste principles more effective and efficient?

One of the main challenges that Tamara and Simon encountered is the complexity of zero waste and particularly the non-transparent supply chains that make it hard for them to truly assess whether or not a product really complies with Café spurlos' philosophy and requirements. The traceability of food products as well as the evaluation and prioritization of sustainability criteria requires highly specialized knowledge and is also a very time-consuming process. Thus, it is evident that the complex system of different factors that influence zero waste strategies in the gastronomy industry need to somehow be connected and analyzed in a structured and automated manner. This shows the importance of technology integration and particularly the need for a system of intelligent technology in connection with human society to tackle sustainability issues.

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